

Posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES)

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Abstract:

Purpose of review:

PRES is a clinicoradiological syndrome characterized by acute cerebral endotheliopathy with consecutive disruption of the blood brain barrier and vasogenic oedema. Since its first description in 1996, PRES is increasingly recognised. However, many aspects of this syndrome with its wide spectrum of clinical and radiological features are still incompletely understood. In this review, possible pathophysiological mechanisms, approaches to diagnosis, recent study results on outcome, as well as future directions of research are described.

Recent findings:

Clinical manifestations of PRES include seizures, headache, visual disturbances, altered mental state, and more rarely hemiparesis or aphasia. Vasogenic oedema predominantly occurs in the parieto-occipital region, but lesions affecting formerly called “atypical” regions such as frontal lobe, cerebellum or basal ganglia are common. If treated early and adequately i.e. by removal of the underlying cause, PRES has a favourable prognosis, but neurological residual symptoms and even mortality can occur, particularly in patients with complications such as intracranial haemorrhage.

Summary:

In summary, validated diagnostic criteria and algorithms are warranted to standardise the diagnosis of PRES. This is essential for further research and future prospective studies that should investigate risk factors for unfavourable outcome and identify the roles of imaging features, clinical symptoms and other **biomarkers** in predicting **outcome**.

Keywords:

Posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome, prognosis, vasogenic oedema,
intracranial haemorrhage

Introduction:

Posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES) refers to a clinical and radiological disease entity that was first described by Hinchey and colleagues in the “*New England Journal of Medicine*” in 1996 (1). A reversible subcortical vasogenic brain oedema defines the disorder, predominantly involving the parieto-occipital region in patients along with acute neurological deficits (e.g. visual disturbances, seizures, headache, altered mental state). Acute endothelial injury with breakdown of the blood brain barrier (BBB) and subsequent brain oedema is thought to cause PRES in the setting of various diseases and conditions such as renal failure, hypertensive crisis, sepsis, cytotoxic drugs, autoimmune disorders, and pre-eclampsia or eclampsia (2). In general, PRES is considered to be reversible (hence the name), both clinically and radiologically with a favourable prognosis if treated fast and adequately i.e. by eliminating the underlying toxic condition. During the last decades with increased availability and use of brain MR imaging, recognition and diagnosis of PRES has rapidly increased (3). In addition, the scientific literature on PRES, albeit mostly based on case reports and case series is growing exponentially. However, many aspects of this disease entity called PRES with its broad clinico-radiological spectrum posit a challenge for the future: PRES patients may be encountered in many clinical disciplines besides neurology such as nephrology, intensive care medicine, oncology, gynecology, haematology, rheumatology, solid organ transplantation surgery and even pediatrics (4). Recent studies could demonstrate that clinical and radiological features are more often “atypical” and non-reversible than thought in the past (5).

Furthermore, validated diagnostic criteria for PRES are lacking and mostly all our knowledge of clinical and radiological features of PRES (including risk factors,

course of disease, data on prognosis and outcome) is based on observational data typically from single-center, retrospective studies or case-series.

In this review, we will describe current knowledge on PRES pathophysiology, common and atypical clinical and radiological findings with a focus on recent studies, approaches to diagnosis of PRES, available study results on outcome, management implications, and future research directions.

Pathophysiology and aetiology of PRES

In normal conditions, cerebral blood flow (CBF) is maintained constant despite changes in cerebral perfusion pressure within the range of mean arterial pressure (MAP) 60 to 150 mmHG. Adaptive changes of the cerebral arteriolar wall diameters mainly regulate this so-called “cerebral autoregulation” in response to a) transmural pressure registered by endothelial mechanoreceptors, b) chemical factors (i.e. hypo- or hypercapnia), and c) the autonomic nervous system (6). The neurovascular unit controls CBF regulation as a complex intercellular communication system composed by neurons, astrocytes, endothelial cells of BBB, myocytes, pericytes as well as extracellular matrix components that are all contributing to stabilize the cerebral circulation (7). In addition, the cerebral endothelium also regulates the vascular tone via secretion of vasodilators (e.g. nitric oxide, hyperpolarizing factor) and vasoconstrictors (e.g. endothelin 1). The proportion of sympathetic neurogenic influence on cerebral autoregulation is still under investigation. However, the traditional hypothesis assumes that due to the relatively sparse sympathetic innervation in the posterior fossa, the occipital region is more susceptible to hyperperfusion.

While clinical conditions and toxins that may cause PRES are numerous, a couple of theories of the pathophysiological mechanisms in PRES have been postulated. The most recognized “vasogenic” theory proposes that a severe increase in blood pressure leads to impaired cerebral autoregulation followed by hyperperfusion, endothelial injury, breakdown of the BBB and secondary vasogenic oedema (8,9). This theory might be particularly true for severe hypertension that exceeds the upper MAP limit of cerebral autoregulation (>140-150 mmHG). However, in more than 50% of PRES cases no severe hypertension was found in retrospective studies (5,10). Thus, other theories have been proposed, even though the final end path of the syndrome with endothelial dysfunction, subsequent disruption of BBB, local hypoperfusion and vasogenic oedema is similar. Proposed theories comprise the “cytotoxic”, “immunogenic”, and the “neuropeptide/ cerebral vasoconstriction” theory (3). The “cytotoxic” concept of PRES pathophysiology formulates that the primary damage is due to toxic triggers such as chemicals or exogenous toxins including chemotherapeutics (cyclophosphamide, vincristine) or immunosuppressant drugs (tacrolimus, cyclosporine) (11,12). The “immunogenic” theory emphasizes the relevant role of the immune system on the brain that leads to endotheliopathy with increased endothelial permeability and vasogenic oedema mainly mediated via T-cell activation and cytokine release such as histamine, free radicals, and nitric oxide (8,13). Finally, according to the “neuropeptide” theory, the release of potent vasoconstrictors such as endothelin 1 and thromboxane A2 leads to severe cerebral vasoconstriction with subsequent endothelial dysfunction and hypoperfusion that might cause cerebral oedema and brain ischemia if not reversed (13). This concept is supported by vessel imaging studies that found a focal or diffuse cerebral vasoconstriction (MRI, catheter angiography) in 40 (85%) out of 47 patients with

PRES (14). These angiographic findings are usually reversible and occur predominantly in the posterior circulation. However, one has to consider that PRES studies that predominantly include patients with vessel imaging are prone to selection bias. In summary, mechanisms leading to endotheliopathy in PRES are numerous. Given the heterogeneity of underlying disease conditions and toxic triggers, it is very likely that - at least in the initial phase of the disease- different pathophysiological mechanisms and combinations thereof play a role. However, studies investigating pathophysiological subgroups in PRES are lacking.

Bartynski and co-workers were the first to propose the following etiologic categories: a) immunosuppression (immunosuppressive medications such as tacrolimus, cyclosporine a, or/and mycophenolate mofetil after solid organ transplantation or bone marrow transplantation with), b) chemotherapy, c) autoimmune disorders (e.g. systemic lupus erythematoses), d) infections/ sepsis, e) pre-eclampsia/ eclampsia, f) others (acute renal failure, other toxic substance such as cocaine or unknown)(5,15). In our retrospective Berlin PRES study including 151 patients with PRES we reported the following distribution of etiologies: 21% immunosuppression, 19% chemotherapy, 18% eclampsia/ preclampsia, 19% autoimmune disorders, 9% infection/ sepsis, 13% other or unknown (16). In addition, renal dysfunction and/or failure is present in more than 50% all patients with PRES and therefore one of the most frequent comorbidities, particularly in autoimmune disorders and (10,17). Autoimmune disorders have been shown to the largest etiological subtype in PRES including thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura, primary sclerosing cholangitis, rheumatoid arthritis, Sjögren syndrome, polyarteriitis nodosa, systemic sclerosis, systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) , granulomatosis with polyangiitis, Crohn´s disease, neuromyelitis optica (17–20).

Moreover, reports on drugs and toxic agents that could trigger PRES are numerous and rapidly increasing in the current literature (21). Furthermore, PRES might develop even weeks and months after initiation of drug therapy (e.g. application of immunosuppressive drugs after transplantation).

Diagnostic criteria, clinical and radiological features

To date, established and validated diagnostic criteria for PRES are lacking. Given the fact that clinical and imaging features of PRES are mostly non-specific, PRES is often diagnosed by exclusion of other disorders such as autoimmune encephalitis or posterior stroke.

Therefore, Fugate and co-authors proposed the following algorithm for the diagnosis of PRES (2): 1) at least one acute neurological symptoms (seizure, altered mental state, headache, visual disturbances), 2) **more or equal than one risk factor** (severe hypertension, renal failure, immunosuppressant drugs or chemotherapy, eclampsia, autoimmune disorder), 3) brain imaging with bilateral vasogenic oedema, cytotoxic oedema with patterns of PRES or normal brain imaging, 4) no other alternative diagnosis. The authors stated that the proposed algorithm could identify cases that do not fit the typical and restrictive boundaries of previous definitions (such as presence of bilateral occipital oedema in brain imaging) and comprises the full range of features of PRES.

Clinically, PRES is typically characterized by acute onset of neurological symptoms such as seizures, headache, visual disturbances (hemianopsia, blurred vision, visual neglect, visual hallucinations, cortical blindness), altered mental state (confusion, drowsiness, coma), hemiparesis, aphasia/ dysarthria, ataxia/ dizziness, and various other focal neurologic signs (5,13,17,22,23). Seizures and headache are

the most common symptoms followed by visual disturbances and altered mental state. Frequencies of initial neurological symptoms in 151 PRES patients from the retrospective Berlin PRES study were seizures in 66 % of patients, visual disturbances in 30%, altered mental state in 40% and paresis in 12% (16). Similar to adults, seizures are also the most common presenting symptoms in children with PRES that could be found in approx. 90% (24,25). In the absence of guidelines and algorithms, clinical experience is the most important factor in making the right diagnosis. Given the non-specificity of neurological symptoms, brain MRI is crucial in diagnosing PRES, particularly to exclude other diagnoses. A list of possible differential diagnoses is shown in **table 1**.

Radiologically, the classic, so-called “typical” MRI findings are symmetric (reversible) T2 or Fluid-attenuated inversion recovery imaging (FLAIR) hyperintensities located in the occipital and parietal region caused by vasogenic oedema (**figure 1a**).

Vasogenic oedema distribution in PRES can vary from very sparse to holohemispheric (**figure 2**) while in principal all cerebral structures can be affected as shown in the synopsis (**figure 3**). Several characteristic patterns of vasogenic oedema in PRES have been described before (5,15). The four most common patterns are shown in **figure 1**: a) the parieto-occipital (PO) pattern with vasogenic oedema predominantly in the parieto-occipital lobes, b) the superior frontal sulcus (SFS) pattern with oedema predominantly along the anterior and media watershed region located in the depth of the SFS, c) the holohemispheric watershed pattern, with oedema located in both anterior and posterior, medial and lateral watershed zones d) the central pattern with vasogenic oedema located preferentially in the deep white matter, basal ganglia, thalami, brainstem and pons. Percentage distributions of patterns are ~50-55% for PO, 21-27% for SFS, 23-29% for

holohemispheric, and ~13% for central pattern in large retrospective studies (15,16). Importantly, neither the patterns themselves nor the severity of vasogenic oedema are related to severity of clinical symptoms (10,17), whereas severe oedema lesions have been found to be associated with poor outcome in one study (18). In addition, oedema lesions affecting formerly called “atypical” regions such as frontal lobe, thalamus, basal ganglia or cerebellum are frequent and mostly accompanied by more classic manifestations as detailed above, e.g. typical parieto-occipital lesions (2).

Diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) including calculated apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) maps are useful to distinguish vasogenic oedema with increased ADC-values from cytotoxic oedema with decreased ADC-values (i.e. diffusion restriction, **figure 4**). Restricted diffusion can be seen in 15-30% of cases. In 151 patients with PRES, we found presence of cytotoxic oedema in 46 patients (16). Cytotoxic oedema in PRES might be due to severe local hypoperfusion in the setting of disturbed autoregulation with transient overshooting vasoconstriction, secondary to the toxic effects of drugs or endogenous metabolites on cellular oxidative phosphorylation as well as due to increase of local tissue pressure caused by vasogenic oedema with consecutive impairment of local microcirculation. Cytotoxic oedema is generally associated with irreversible structural brain damage and might be associated with residual clinical symptoms and unfavourable outcome (16,26). However, we have to consider that territorial infarcts are rare and DWI lesions are small and mostly occur in the middle of vasogenic oedema. **Figure 6** shows examples of lesion diffusivity in PRES. Furthermore, intracranial haemorrhage is a frequent complication in PRES and occurs in 10-25% of cases (5,10,17,27,28). Types of haemorrhages are intraparenchymal or lobar haemorrhages, sulcal subarachnoid haemorrhage (SAH) and microbleeds as shown in **figure 5**. Blood

vessel irregularities consistent with vasoconstriction have been reported in up to 30% of cases (**figure 6**) (17,29). PRES has also been described as an overlap with or a complication of reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome (30).

Prognosis and Outcome:

Even though PRES has gained increased attention since its first description more than two decades ago, data on outcome from prospective studies are still lacking. In most cases PRES has a good short- and long-term prognosis if treated fast and adequately and MRI findings and clinical symptoms are reversible after several hours or days (31). However, cerebral haemorrhage or ischemia as well as irreversible neurological deficits or death occur. Studies reported complete resolution of oedema and clinical recovery in 70 - 90% of cases (18,26,31,32). A recent meta-analysis that included six studies with 448 cases found that only haemorrhage was significantly associated with poor outcome in adjusted analyses with pooled OR of 4.9 (95%CI 3.9-6.2), whereas aetiology of eclampsia was protective with OR of 0.2 (CI% 0.15-0.4)(33). However, given the heterogeneity of studies with differences in outcome variables (e.g. in-hospital death, functional outcome with modified Rankin scale, Glasgow outcome scale), study populations and case numbers, results have to be interpreted with caution. Furthermore, mortality and morbidity in PRES are also dependent on the underlying disease i.e. women with PRES in eclampsia have a better prognosis than patient with chemotherapy-associated PRES in incurable cancer patients) .

In all available studies, death occurred in 8- 17% of PRES cases and poor outcome was found in 26 - 36% of patients dependent on the specific outcome measure (18,34–36). In a recent adjusted analysis in 151 patients, we found that increasing

age, high levels of C-reactive protein, occurrence of SAH, altered mental state as initial clinical presentation, and altered coagulation parameters were independently associated with in-hospital death (16). In addition, in the same study population severe oedema was related to poor outcome at discharge, whereas aetiology of pre-/eclampsia was associated with favourable outcome (18). PRES recurrence was described in 5–10% of patients. Main risk factor was uncontrolled hypertension (37).

Management implications:

PRES has to be treated early, adequately and sufficiently long. The most important steps in the acute clinical management are a) confirmation of diagnosis with prompt cerebral MRI including DWI and ADC-values, b) removal of the underlying cause e.g. discontinuation of immunosuppressant drug intake and c) lowering of elevated blood pressure if moderate to severe hypertension is present. Acute hypertensive treatment should aim for a relative reduction of 20-30% in the first hours after onset according to hypertensive crisis guidelines (38). Patients should be transferred to an intensive care unit or monitoring station for continuous blood pressure monitoring (preferentially by intraarterial line) and - if needed - intravenous application of antihypertensive medication (e.g. urapidil). However, nitroglycerin should be avoided in antihypertensive management, since aggravation of PRES has been described before (39). If eclampsia or pre-eclampsia is diagnosed, administration of magnesium sulfate is indicated as well as a prompt delivery of the fetus (8,13,40). For the treatment of acute symptomatic seizures, antiepileptic drugs should be applied intravenously with agents such as intravenous benzodiazepines or levetiracetam (41).

Recent findings:

Recently, two studies investigated the spectrum of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) parameters findings in PRES (42,43). In both studies, CSF protein was significantly elevated in PRES patients and levels of CSF protein were positively correlated with severity of oedema. In addition, the authors found an elevated CSF/serum albumin quotient (age-adjusted) in three out of four of these patients that was also associated with severe oedema. Pleocytosis was rare (< 10%) and if present only mild. Median cell counts were 2 (IQR 1–4; max. 41) per μl (42).

Furthermore, a recent EEG study found that non-convulsive seizures (NCS) and epileptiform patterns such as periodic discharges (PD) during continuous EEG monitoring were present in 62% percent out of 32 eligible PRES patients and occurred predominantly in the posterior region. Although frequency of NCS and PD was not associated with severity of clinical symptoms, patients with PD/ NCS had worse outcome measured with the Glasgow outcome scale (44).

Moreover, Allen and colleagues found that 7% of SAH patients developed PRES during induced hypertension. PRES occurred most often when MAP was raised above the levels of cerebral autoregulation threshold (>140 mmHG) during aggressive, induced hypertension in SAH. This finding supports the classic “vasogenic” theory that severe hypertension exceeding the autoregulation threshold is the key risk factor for PRES (45).

No evidence exists so far on pharmacological treatment of vasogenic oedema in PRES. Recently, a further study assessed the prevalence of steroid therapy in PRES patients at the time of symptom onset and investigated the relationship between steroid therapy and extent of vasogenic oedema. Steroid therapy at time of PRES onset was present in approx. 45% of patients. However, no

benefit of steroid therapy on oedema severity was found in adjusted analyses (46).

Certainly, given the retrospective study design and low case numbers, results has to be interpreted with caution.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, PRES is a clinicoradiological syndrome characterized by acute cerebral endotheliopathy with consecutive disruption of BBB and vasogenic oedema predominantly in the posterior region of the brain. PRES is increasingly recognised during the last two decades, but many aspects of this syndrome with its wide spectrum of clinical and radiological feature are still unclear.

In particular, established and validated diagnostic criteria as well as clinical algorithms are needed to standardise the diagnosis of PRES. This is essential for future research and to setup future prospective observational studies that could investigate clinical outcomes, identify the roles of imaging features, clinical symptoms and other biomarker in predicting prognosis and establish risk factors for unfavorable outcome.

Key points:

- PRES is a clinicoradiological syndrome with typical MRI findings characterized by acute cerebral endotheliopathy with consecutive disruption of blood brain barrier and vasogenic oedema predominantly in the parieto-occipital region of the brain
- Pathophysiology is not clear, but acute cerebral endotheliopathy might be triggered by severe hypertension that exceeds the threshold of cerebral

autoregulation, by endogenous or exogenous toxins such as chemotherapy or immunosuppressant drugs or by severe cerebral vasoconstriction and spasms induced via neuropeptides

- The most common clinical manifestations are seizures, headache, visual disturbances such as hemianopia, blurred vision or cortical blindness, altered mental state such as confusion or coma as well as more rarely severe focal signs such as hemiparesis or aphasia
- PRES has a relatively good short- and long-term prognosis and MRI findings and clinical symptoms are reversible if the syndrome is treated early and adequately. Main treatment is the removal of the underlying cause (e.g. immunosuppressant drugs) and lowering of blood pressure is mandatory in cases with severe hypertension

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Tables and figures legends:

Figure 1:

Edema patterns

Four topographic lesion distribution patterns have been described in PRES:

A) parieto-occipital (PO) pattern with vasogenic edema predominantly in the parieto-occipital lobes (right axial FLAIR, left sagittal T2w)

B) Superior frontal sulcus (SFS) pattern with predominant edema along the ACA-MCA watershed located in the depth of the SFS

C) Holohemispheric watershed pattern with predominant involvement of the ACA/MCA, ACA/PCA and MCA/PCA watershed regions

D) Central pattern with vasogenic edema located preferentially in the deep white matter, basal ganglia, thalami, brainstem and pons

Figure 2:

Edema severity

Vasogenic edematization in PRES can vary from very subtle to strikingly holohemispheric

Figure 3:

Edema location

In PRES all cerebral structures can be affected by vasogenic edema. From left to right:

Upper row: frontal and parietal lobes, temporal and occipital lobes, hippocampi

Middle row: basal ganglia, thalami, hypothalami, midbrain

Lower row: pons, cerebellum, medulla oblongata, corpus callosum

Figure 4:

Diffusivity in PRES

- A) Vasogenic edema, characterized by increased signal in T2, normal signal or variable T2 shine through on DWI and elevated ADC values
- B) Cytotoxic edema, characterized by T2 signal elevation, DWI hypersignal and corresponding ADC reduction (circle). Vasogenic edema is virtually always co-present (arrows)

Figure 5:

Hemorrhagic presentation in PRES

Three types have been recognized:

- A) Lobar hemorrhages, usually centered in the maximum vasogenic edema. These can be detected by CT (not shown), T2*/SWI and conventional sequences.
- B) Microbleeds, either solitary juxtacortical or deep or multiple, only/ best appreciated on T2* or SWI sequences
- C) Localized convexity subarachnoid hemorrhage as detected by CT, FLAIR or T2*/SWI.

Figure 6:

Angiographic findings

Angiographic findings range from normal to multifocal vasospasms as shown here.

Angiographic images after selective left ICA injection in this PRES case reveal multifocal stenoses and dilatations of the distal arterial bed in the ACA/MCA watershed area.

Table 1:

Differential diagnoses of posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES)

Vascular

- Cerebral ischemia (ie posterior stroke)
- Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis
- Intracerebral hemorrhage
- Subcortical leucoaraiosis
- CNS vasculitis
- Reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome

Degenerativ/ Autoimmune

- Acute demyelinating encephalomyelitis
- Multiple sclerosis/ acute disseminated encephalomyelitis
- Other autoimmune encephalitis (e.g. limbic encephalitis, Hashimoto's, Rasmussen, SLE, Behcet's)
- Cerebral Autosomal Dominant Arteriopathy With Subcortical Infarcts and Leukoencephalopathy (CADASIL)
- Mitochondrial encephalopathy, lactic acidosis, and stroke-like episodes (MELAS)
- Creutzfeldt–Jakob disease

Infectious

- Herpes simplex encephalitis
- Other infectious encephalitis
- Progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy

Cancer-related

- Malignancy or tumour (lymphoma, gliomatosis cerebri, metastatic disease)
- Paraneoplastic encephalitis
- Chemotherapy-related demyelinating disorder
- Radiation necrosis

Metabolic

- Metabolic encephalopathy
 - Osmotic demyelinating syndrome (central pontine myelinolysis)
 - Toxic leukoencephalopathy
-

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Etiology and toxic association in 151 patients with reversible posterior encephalopathy syndrome

Other/ Unknown

13,2%

Pre-/ Eclampsia

18,5%

Chemotherapy

19,2%

Immunosuppression

21,2%

Sepsis/ Infection

8,6%

Autoimmune Disorders

19,2%

Initial neurological symptoms in 151 patients with posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome

A

B

C

D

T2/FLAIR

DWI

ADC

A

B

